

Ecology Informed Innovation: Leveraging GIS, Digital Data Capture, and Data-Driven Solutions for Biodiversity Net Gain

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Summary

Environment Bank has pioneered a national network of forward funded habitat banks to support the Biodiversity Net Gain (BNG) legislation introduced in February 2024, requiring at least a 10% net gain in biodiversity. The Data and GIS team plays a critical role by developing robust data systems, automating workflows, and implementing a comprehensive data pipeline using ESRI's ArcGIS suite. This innovative approach integrates digital data capture, spatial analysis, and stakeholder reporting to streamline ecological assessments and manage BNG unit stock over a 30+ year lifecycle. With 6,500+ acres of habitat creation underway, Environment Bank leads in high-integrity BNG solutions.

KEYWORDS: Biodiversity Net Gain, BNG, Ecology, Habitat Recovery, Biodiversity Restoration, Data Quality

1. Introduction

Since the Environment Act passed in 2021, Environment Bank have been creating a national network of habitat banks in preparation for the critically needed, mandatory environmental regulations to reverse severe biodiversity loss in England. The Biodiversity Net Gain (BNG) legislation, implemented by The Department for Environment, Food & Rural Affairs (2024), requires new developments to deliver a minimum BNG of 10% to meet new stringent planning requirements. Many developers and Local Planning Authorities (LPAs) have been working to prepare for the change in planning law, but Environment Bank, has pioneered a nationwide network of recovery sites to generate available BNG units ensuring a market for off-site units from the outset of the legislative change. Environment Bank's land leasing model provides many landowners a welcome diversification and guaranteed income alongside benefitting for the environment.

The Data and GIS Team at Environment Bank, have been an integral part of this, building robust data systems, automating processes, strengthening the ability to collect, manage, visualise, and ensuring the quality of data across the business. Ensuring commercial and ecological integrity, while delivering the best outcome for nature through data-driven solutions.

2. The Solution

Global biodiversity loss is now a widely accepted crisis (Wood *et al*, 2013), but goals to reduce the rate of biodiversity loss have mostly not been achieved (Johnson *et al*, 2017). The UK is one of the most nature depleted nations in the world (*Environment Act, 2021*) and in addition to preventing further loss the UK Government now recognise the need to intervene to encourage restoration. Environment Bank have been working to develop solutions to encourage investment in nature restoration since 2006, and

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worked with Natural England in the lead up to the legislative change, and over the last 3 years have accelerated the development of data systems and have implemented a full digital workflow for BNG creation and management. This also included the launch of an internal BNG unit stock management system, allowing Environment Bank to manage Biodiversity Unit stock and sales data for the full 30+ year life cycle of network of habitat banks servicing off-site unit requirements across the country. When the BNG legislation came into effect on the 12th February 2024, Environment Bank, had data workflows and systems ready for the development of suitable recovery sites and the sale of the BNG units, ensuring unit availability for development as an ‘off the shelf’ solution from the BNG launch date.

The digital workflow has increased efficiency, streamlining land and ecological assessment processes from data collection to analysis and dissemination of data and results, ultimately increasing the effectiveness of the teams’ nature recovery work. Rigorous quality assurance has ensured consistency and transparency of data, which, as a trusted provider of off-site BNG units has helped underpin all restoration work. The data-driven solution facilitated by a digital data workflow can enable one custodian the ownership, such as a geospatial professional to maintain efficiency and accuracy across the stages.

3. Site Evaluation and Digital Data Capture Workflow

The starting point of the geospatial data journey for a habitat bank begins with the ‘onboarding’ of a site. A desk-based data trawling tool that adds the site to Environment Bank’s ArcGIS online portal and accesses relevant environmental data from various REST services and other through API’s, data that is used to help determine the viability of a site for restoration, allowing us to ensure assessments are being done on the latest versions of datasets. Potential sites will then be reviewed by our expert ecology teams with additional local knowledge that may not yet be factored in where not available via API for the previous step, such as the Local Nature Recovery Strategies (LNRSs), where published, and other local nature priorities.

If sites has good potential for restoration the next stage involves most of the field data collection to create a full site baseline. Site visits are conducted by our Ecology and Land team to meet the landowner and begin working with them to see if our model of BNG can help with farm business. Along side the our ecologists will digitally map the existing baseline habitats, starting from a pre-digitised polygon base, and perform in depth habitat condition assessments. This survey protocol precisely follows the DEFRA BNG metric survey guidance, built in a bespoke ArcGIS online environment utilising Fieldmaps and Survbey123.

The collected data is processed using geoprocessing script tools and processed in mapping software for ecological quality assurance and proposed habitat restoration design. Cartographic input, involving some data management and cleaning, produces figures for geospatial context into reporting and plans required for site progression (Figure 1 **Error! Reference source not found.**).

Figure 1 Initial Site Visualisation Graphic for Landowners

During the latter part of a habitat bank selection process and the site designs are finalised, A full Data Quality Assurance & Control (QA/QC) ensures data accuracy, integrity and transparency for auditing purposes. This involves a full topology assessment, attribute checks, and meta data checks of a site's data, the primary focus is on the spatial data layers that underpin all BNG calculations for a site, metric baseline habitats (points, lines polygons), metric proposed habitats (points, lines, polygons) and our site boundary. In addition, the process checks all Environment Bank, and sub-contractor, originated data to ensure it meets our data and meta data standards (eg. Soils, Hydrology, further ecological & species-specific survey data).

A 2nd stage QC is also performed for diligence and consistency, if there are design changes required after these steps a post QC change process is followed to record this. Figure 2 shows a simplified version of the workflow.

Figure 2 Simplified GIS workflow diagram of input at key stages of a habitat bank selection process

Once the Sites have been designed, planned and reviewed; they proceed to a habitat delivery phase, including digging ponds, planting trees, nutrient stripping, seeding etc., which is followed by 30 years of routine habitat management, ecological monitoring and any additional required works. This work can be managed and tracked using our suite of data systems including our ArcGIS online environment and integrations project management tools and systems.

Environment Bank have also developed a bespoke multi-site, multi-sale, BNG unit stock management system with full traceability of where units are being generated through to where they are being used to help meet our customers’ off-site BNG requirements for planning.

The system takes the metric calculations, unit uplift, temporal and spatial multipliers and applies trading rules. It was developed in-house as a custom SQL server database and with PowerBI front end UI and allows trackability of BNG units and sites through the full lifecycle. This system has now been upgraded and integrated with Environment Bank’s CRM to allow seamless management of unit stock along side sales, marketing and site data to vastly improve the internal user experience and lay the groundwork for future system development and integration.

This ecological data pipeline feeds the BNG stock management system, giving our colleagues live data on what units are available, what may be upcoming, and the geographical location for customer and Local Planning Authority engagement. Allowing these teams to work with planners and developers to help them understand BNG and meet their planning requirements. In turn the information received from clients, feeds back into the siting, development and planning of our future habitat bank sites, in terms of location, scale and the design of ecologically appropriate habitats to meet requirements.

4. Conclusion

As a relatively new concept, there was no ‘out of the box’ scalable system for off-site BNG, and no data model for managing multiple, separate, fractional unit transactions for off-site BNG gains. Using ESRI’s ArcGIS suite of applications, custom scripts and APIs and a semi-customised CRM, Environment Bank has developed a full digital data capture workflow for BNG habitat creation,

management, monitoring and unit sales. This includes automated protocols in place to ensure data quality, keeping the high-ecological integrity BNG units underpinned by high-integrity data.

An advanced data workflow and quality assurance process for BNG has streamlined the spatial data lifecycle. The process of initial habitat bank onboarding to fully restored ecosystem, has been and still is a new venture for most organisations. Streamlining digital field data capture with the ability to map and record precise condition assessments for each habitat, across a national network of sites for over 30 plus years of management and monitoring for habitat restoration work. Data management and GIS provides early site design optioneering with clear mapping and visualisation, providing spatial context in the form of accurate cartographic figures, essential for reporting to stakeholders.

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6. References

Department for Environment, Food & Rural Affairs (2024). *Understanding Biodiversity Net Gain*. Available at: <https://www.gov.uk/guidance/understanding-biodiversity-net-gain> (Accessed: 30/01/2025)

Environment Act 2021, c. 30. Available at: <https://www.legislation.gov.uk/ukpga/2021/30/contents> (Accessed: 30/01/2025).

Goodchild, M.F. and Longley, P.A., (1999). *The future of GIS and spatial analysis*. Geographical information systems, 1, pp.567-580.

Johnson, C.N., Balmford, A., Brook, B.W., Buettel, J.C., Galetti, M., Guangchun, L. and Wilmshurst, J.M., (2017) *Biodiversity losses and conservation responses in the Anthropocene*. *Science*, 356(6335), pp.270-275.

Wood, A., Stedman-Edwards, P. and Mang, J., (2013). *The root causes of biodiversity loss*. Routledge.

7. Biographies

George holds a BSc in Environmental Sciences from the University of York and an MSc in GIS from the University of Aberdeen, specializing in spatial planning for nature recovery. He leads the Data and GIS team at Environment Bank, focusing on team development, automation, systems integration, and business intelligence.

Tara has a BSc in Geography from the University of Leeds and experience of working in the environmental sector and on marine GIS projects, conducting field surveys and data interpretation. Tara's interests are in fluvial geomorphology, cartography and nature, and how to use data to develop innovative solutions ion these areas.

Sophie has a BSc in Biology from the University of Southampton, a MSc in Wildlife Conservation from the University of Reading, and post-graduate research experience in Sri Lanka, India, and Canada. She has worked in research, scientific publishing and GIS. Her work and interests include spatial and non-spatial data focussing on data integrity, automation scripting, and team development.

Hannah has a BSc in Geography from the University of Hull and is a Chartered Geographer (specialising in GIS) with the Royal Geographical Society with IBG. She has experience of working with GIS in the public and private sector. Her interests lie in digital field surveying, geology and soils.